

Enhancing Contributions, and Challenges of Home Gardening Practices of Households in Ondo

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Abstract

The general objective of this study was to investigate the contributions and challenges of home gardening practices of households in Ondo town. Specifically, the study identified the foods commonly produced in home gardens, determined the estimated income realized by households from the sale of home garden produce and problems associated with home gardening. The population was made up of households in Ondo town. A purposive sample of 150 households was selected. Questionnaire, oral interview and observation were used for data collection. Frequency and percentages were used for data analysis. Major findings include: 26.0% of the households have their diet supplemented with products obtained from the home gardens. About thirty one and thirty percent of households claimed to realize between N10,001 to N20,000 and N30,001 to N40,000 annually (respectively) from sale of products in their gardens.

Introduction

Food security implies physical and economic access, at all times to sufficient, safe and nutritious food to meet dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (FAO, 2005). Food security involves ensuring a nutritionally adequate and safe food supply at both the national and household levels. In addition, it includes a reasonable degree of sustainability in the supply of food during a given year and all year round. It also demands access by each household to sufficient food to

meet the needs of its members. A household is considered food secure when its occupants do not live in hunger or fear of starvation (Wikipedia 2010). This means that each household must always have the ability, the knowledge and the resources to produce or procure the foods needed to provide for all the nutritional requirements of the household members, that is, a balanced diet providing all necessary energy, protein and micronutrients (Olumakaiye and Ajayi, 2006).

Generally, food security can be

attained via three sources: own production, purchase and aids. Of these, the only dependable one is own production as food aids is transitory while purchase is influenced by purchasing power (Ndaeyo, 2007).

Access to stable and suitable food supplies is a precondition for the establishment of food security at the household level. Sustainability of food supplies refers to the capacity to ensure the long term stability of the household food supply and the ability of households to meet consumption and livelihood needs on a continuous basis. In addition, in a food-secure community, the growing, processing and distribution of food is regionally based, socially just and environmentally sustainable (www.communitycouncil.ca/resources/glossary.html).

One of the ways to achieve the so important stable and sustainable food supply at the household level is through home gardening. Small food gardens near the family home have traditionally made an important contribution to family nutrition. Home gardens can help supply a family with substantial quantities of a variety of food all year round. Home gardening involves the cultivation of an area of land around the home for the production of traditional staple foods which typically include roots and tubers, green leafy vegetables, legumes and fruits. These are rich in micronutrients – such as Vitamins A and C, iron and sometimes Vitamin B

– and in some cases contain appreciable amounts of protein and oil/fat; small animals, insects and poultry which are good sources of complete protein and haem iron (Savage and Burgess 2000). Home garden is sometimes referred to as mixed, backyard, kitchen, farm yard, roof top garden, compound or homestead garden (Marsh 1994).

In recent years, many people's traditional diets have changed. More processed foods are now eaten. Rural farmers may now grow crops to sell rather than for family use. This means they may grow fewer crop varieties, particularly of vegetables. Wild leaves, roots and berries traditionally harvested as food may no longer be available as a result of deforestation and lack of access to communal land. Because of these trends, the diets of many poor people have lost their original variety of traditional foods and they lack enough income to buy a varied and adequate diet. Home gardens can help improve family nutrition, encourage varieties, improve health, produce medicinal plants and save money (Horne, 2005). Home garden foods also have an important "safety net" function. During the lean season, when the staple foods have been depleted and before the new harvest is ready, home garden foods can augment or replenish family supplies.

In addition to producing food, the sale of home garden produce can make a substantial contribution to

household income. The income from home garden can pay for daily essentials and services, such as soap, clothes, school fees, medicines and farm inputs that cannot be produced by the household. Important farm development activities take place in home garden and generate inputs for other farming activities. For example, a home garden can produce planting materials such as sweet potatoes vines, cassava cuttings, fruit tree seedling and vegetable seeds. When animals are part of a home garden (e.g. sheep, goats, poultry and perhaps pigs) they supply food, income and manure. The animals in turn benefit from unused plant residues such as the stalks of cereals, vegetables and legumes.

For urban households in East Africa who have access to land, either around or close to their home, producing a crop or keeping livestock is often a cultural norm. Since 1990 however, the need for urban agriculture has been strengthened by economic crisis. And while production of crops or livestock on urban land may not be as significant as the production that urban households-or their relatives-earn from rural land, it still makes an important contribution to livelihoods (<http://www.cityfarmer.org/subafrica.html>).

Ndaeyo (2007) examined the contributions of homestead farming to food security in South Eastern Nigeria. The study revealed an estimated yield of selected crops of 20.4, 7.2, 8.7, 22.3,

21.0, 20.4 25.6 and 3.5 tonnes per hectare, per year of yam, cassava, cocoyam, citrus species, pineapple, plantain, banana and maize, respectively to Nigeria's food output. The study also revealed that most members of the rural households derived a lot of vitamins, proteins and minerals from the consumption of some crops that can hardly be cultivated in distant farms. Agboola (1993) had earlier reported that any crop or plant species that are needed for daily consumption or frequent use by the farmer and his household may be found within homesteads as well as livestock kept as sources of food and income.

Unfortunately, home gardens have rarely received official recognition and families often lack the necessary resources, knowledge and inputs to produce crops as effectively as possible. These major constraints need to be removed if the home garden farming systems are to be successfully promoted.

Objectives of the study

The general objective of the study was to investigate the contributions and challenges of home gardening practices of households in Ondo town. Specifically, the study

- determined the contributions of home garden to household food security in Ondo town.
- identified the foods commonly produced in home gardens of the study area.
- estimated the income realized by

households from the sale of home garden produce.

- identified problems associated with home gardening in the study area.

Methodology

Area of the Study: The study was carried out in Ondo town of Ondo State. Ondo town is located in Ondo West Local Government Area (OWLGA) of Ondo State and it is the main urban area of Ondo West LGA. Most households in Ondo town are usually surrounded by spaces that are used for small gardens.

Design of the Study: The descriptive survey research design was used for this study. This design involves the study of large population by selecting a representative sample to discover relative incidence distribution and interrelations of variables. The result of the representative sample can be inferred or generalized.

Population for the Study: Comprised all homemakers of households with home garden in Ondo town of Ondo State. The estimated population of households in Ondo town is one hundred and twenty-six thousand (Source: Ondo West LGA secretariat, 2010). Cultivation of small gardens around the house is majorly done by females, hence the choice of homemakers as the population for the study.

Sample for the Study: One hundred and fifty urban households with home gardens were selected for the study through purposive sampling technique. The sample was taken from Ondo town which is the most developed town in OWLGA.

Instrument for Data Collection: Questionnaire, oral interview and observation were used for data collection. Closed and open ended questionnaire was drafted by the researcher. The open ended aspect of the questionnaire consisted of items which sought information on the types of food materials grown on home gardens. The closed aspect of the questionnaire contained items which sought information on contribution of home gardens to household food security estimated income and problems associated with home gardening. Content of the questionnaire was used as oral interview for non literate respondents. Observation guide on types of food items grown in home gardens was used to ascertain the authenticity of information provided by respondents. The questionnaire was given to three experts in food and nutrition for face and content validation.

Data Collection and Analysis Techniques: One hundred and fifty copies of the validated questionnaire were distributed by the researchers to selected homemakers in the town. All the one hundred and fifty copies were

retrieved. Literate respondents were given questionnaire to complete by them selves while oral interview was conducted for the non-literate respondents using the questionnaire as a guide. Observation of foods produced in home gardens of respondents were also recorded. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics of frequency count and simple percentage.

Results

i. Demographic Variables:

The findings show that 53.3% of the 150 households involved in the study were headed by males. About 46.7% of the households had female heads who were responsible for ensuring household food security. The result showed a high level of literacy as 54.7

of respondents had tertiary education. Data on employment status show that 32.0% of respondents had no job at that moment. Up to 66.7% were employed and have access to regular source of income which is a very important factor in household food security and economic stability. With regard to age, 50% of the respondents were between 21 to 30 years. On marital status, 46.7% were single mothers.

ii. Contributions of Home Garden to Household Food Security

Home garden makes five contributions to household food security in Ondo town as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Percentage Responses on Contributions of Home Garden to Household Food Security

S/N	Contribution of Home Garden	Frequency	%
1	Improve family food supplies and nutrition	39	26.0
2	Leisure time activity	14	9.3
3	Provide some income	70	46.7
4	Food reserves for emergencies and special occasions	22	14.7
5	Reduce weeds and bush around the home	5	3.3
Total		150	100.0

Table 1 reveals that 26.0% households identified that home garden improve their family food supplies and nutrition, 9.3% said it is a sort of leisure time activity and about half of the total household involved in the study, (46.7%) said home garden provides some income for them. In addition, 14.7% of households identified that home garden functions

as food reserves for emergencies and special occasions while 3.3% said it reduces weeds and bush around the home. It can therefore be inferred from the result presented in the table that about three quarters of households (72.7%) keep home garden mainly to boost their income and family food supplies.

iii. Foods commonly produced in home gardens (80%).

Six fruit trees are grown namely: pawpaw (90%), orange (85%), banana (90%), water melon (50%), cashew (70%) and mango (92%). Seven species of vegetables grown are: tomatoes (20%), okro (80%), pumpkin (80%), spinach (90%), waterleaf (100%), red pepper (80%) and Indian spinach (100%). Five staple crops grown are maize (95%), yam (80%), cassava (98%), sweet potatoes (60%) and cocoyam (100%). Two species of livestock reared are poultry (chicken, turkey and duck) (100%) and goat

iv. Estimated income from sale of home garden produce

Findings on estimated income indicate that 20.0% of households realize N6000 – N10,000 annually, 30.7% realize N10,001 – N20,000, 30.0% realize N20,001 – N30,000, 15.3% realize N30,001 – N40,000 while 4.0% realize over N40,000 annually as income from home garden.

v. Problems associated with home gardening

Table 2: Percentage Responses on Problems Associated with Home Gardening

S/N	Problem	Frequency	%
1.	Insufficient	55	36.7
2.	Inadequate capital	18	12.0
3.	Ruin by domestic animals	48	32.0
4.	Lack of storage facilities	24	16.0
5.	Lack of ready market for produce	6	3.3
	Total	150	100.0

Table 4 shows that 36.7% of respondents had the problem of insufficient land for gardening, 12.0% of respondents were faced with lack of enough capital while 32.0% respondents had problems with domestic animals. Sixteen percent of respondents lack enough storage facilities to keep home garden produce and 3.3% of respondents do not have ready market for produce.

Discussion of Findings

Findings in this study show that home

garden provides some income for 46.7% of the respondents, improves family food supplies and nutrition for 26.0%. it also serves for emergencies and special occasions for 14.7% of respondents. 30.7% and 30.0% of the respondents were able to make a profit of N10,001 to N20,001 to N30,000 annually respectively. Horne (2005) was also of the opinion that home garden foods can augment family food supplies and make substantial contribution to household income. This result is also consistent

with those of Marsh (1994) in Bangladesh and Central America which indicated that home gardening has significant economic benefits and can be a viable strategy for increasing food supplies for family consumption and hence food security.

This study also revealed a diversified farming system in which fruit trees and shrubs are grown alongside different staple crops mixed with livestock production. This finding is consistent with those of (Eboh (1997) on forest and tree products potentials for enhancing food security and economic welfare among rural households in Eastern Nigeria. He reported a pattern of home garden agro forestry which consists of mixed spatial arrangement of trees/shrubs and arable crops like maize, yam, cassava and cocoyam in the same land at the same time or a sequence over time.

Dominant crops in gardens of this study include mango, pawpaw, banana, orange, cashew, water melon, water leaf, Indian spinach, pumpkin, red pepper, okro, pumpkin, cocoyam, cassava, maize, yam. The types of plants identified in this study are in consonance with those reported in the findings of Ndaeyo (2007) in his study of South Eastern Nigeria. He discovered that home garden contributes 20.4, 7.2, 8.7, 22.3, 21.0, 20.4, 25.6 and 3.55 tonnes per hectare per year of yam, cassava, cocoyam, citrus species, pineapple, plantain, banana and maize respectively to

Nigeria's food output. According to Savage and Burgess (2000) and Alexandra (2003),s food production in such diversified farming system will create an increased supply of a variety of foods all through the year, thus enhancing sustainability.

Conclusion

Emerging evidences from the study showed that home gardening can result in tangible benefits for the household, including increased food on the table, extra income, food reserves for emergencies and special occasions, enhanced traditional varieties and ultimately improve family food security and nutrition. Types of food crops grown in home gardens in Ondo town include pawpaw, orange, banana, water melon, cashew, mango, tomatoes, okro, pumpkin, spinach, water leaf, red pepper, Indian spinach, maize, yam, cassava, sweet potato and cocoyam. Access to fresh home grown vegetables, fruits and small animals not only ensures a more balanced diet for families with limited purchasing power, but also increases their self reliance. The sale of surplus food also provide direct benefits, the highest annual income of respondents from home garden (30.7%) was N10,001 - N20,000. However, the major problems associated with home gardening in Ondo town are insufficient land, ruin by domestic animals and lack of storage facilities.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Public enlightenment programmes such as workshops, seminars, radio and television programmes should focus more on home gardening practices in Ondo town. It should be emphasized that such practices will help to boost income of families and provide fresh readily available food crops.
2. Local, State and Federal Government policy makers and planners should make home gardening an important element in food security strategies.
3. More investment in terms of storage facilities and capital should be directed to the improvement of the home gardening sector's output.
4. Measures to increase women's control over land should be out in place as they are primarily responsible for home garden food production.

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